

Synthesis of new carbazole substituted fullerene derivative as an electron acceptor for bulk heterojunction organic photovoltaic cell applications

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Abstract : We design and synthesized 9-hexyl carbazole-3- C_{61} -butric acid methyl ester, (HCvz- C_{61} BM) carbazole based fullerene acceptor derivative used for photovoltaic cell applications. The synthesized HCvz- C_{61} BM acceptor freely soluble in common organic solvents such as $CHCl_3$, CH_2Cl_2 , THF, ODCB and it showed higher LUMO of -3.63 eV. The HCvz- C_{61} BM acceptor showed higher thermal stability of 413 °C. The organic photovoltaic device was fabricated with the configuration of ITO/PEDOT/P3HT : HCvz- C_{61} BM/LiF/Al. It shows the best performance for 1 : 2 weight ratio of P3HT : HCvz- C_{61} BM with PCE of 1.74%, J_{sc} of 6.19 mA/cm², V_{oc} of 0.78 V and FF of 37%.

Keywords : Organic photovoltaics, carbazole, fullerene, PCBM.

Introduction

The bulk heterojunction (BHJ) polymer solar cells (PSCs) have been proved the most successful structure in organic photovoltaic cells applications. The active layer of this BHJ-PSCs device was consisting of electron donor p-type polymers and electron acceptor n-type fullerene derivatives^{1,2}. Several research groups were focused on modification of new donor polymers instead of well optimized P3HT to reach high efficiency and they were achieved, low band gap, broad absorption wave length and power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 3–9.2%^{3,4}. Even though these results are promising, but it has drawback to commercialize the organic solar cells because of their stability issues, and also less PCE compare to inorganic solar cells.

On other hand of the approaches, modification of acceptor such as fullerene (C_{60}) derivatives to achieve higher PCE. The [6,6]-phenyl C_{61} -butyric acid methyl ester (PC₆₁BM) is the best PSCs acceptor material⁵. However, the weak absorption in the visible region and lower-lying LUMO level are their superior limitations to the light harvest in the photovoltaic conversion^{6,7}. Although many research groups focused to solve the above limitations

and they achieved upto 4.0% PCE^{8,9}. Kim *et al.* were synthesized new FCBM and observed 3.1% of PCE¹⁰.

In this article we report synthesis and BHJ-PSCs studies of HCvz- C_{61} BM. Our approach towards the structural modification of PCBM was introduction of carbazole unit instead of fluorene in FCBM.

Results and discussion

The new acceptor HCvz- C_{61} BM was synthesized according to the modified reported procedure^{7,10} and outline in Scheme 1. The *N*-alkylated carbazole (**2**) was prepared by reaction of carbazole (Cvz) and hexylbromides in the presence of NaH used as a base. The alykylated compound was further functionalized by Friedel-Crafts acylation with methyl 5-chloro-5-oxopentanoate. The above keto ester (**3**) reacted with tosylhydrazide in toluene and reaction mixture was purified by column chromatography to get yellow solid with 72% yield of (**4**). Then, the desired fullerene derivative such as HCvz- C_{61} BM was synthesized via the standard diazo addition of compound **4** with fullerene (C_{60}). This was purified with SiO_2 /toluene : hexane (8 : 2) as an eluent. The first fraction was found unreacted C_{60} . The second fraction

Scheme 1. Synthetic route for HCvz-C₆₁BM.

was obtained HCvz-C₆₁BM and the product was precipitated with MeOH. The brown solid was filtered out and washed with MeOH several times to offer 54% of HCvz-C₆₁BM and it was characterized by FT-IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR, UV-Visible spectra, DSC and TGA thermogram.

The FT-IR spectrum shows the characteristic absorption peak of C₆₀ appeared around 525 cm⁻¹, N-CH₂ stretching bands appeared at 2854 cm⁻¹. The band at 1735 cm⁻¹ attributed to the ester carbonyl. The ¹H NMR spectroscopy is used to identify the HCvz-C₆₁BM. The 3rd position of Cvz attached to C₆₀ through sp³ carbon of butyric acid methylester. The Cvz of H₄ appeared as a singlet at 8.61 ppm, the H₁ and H₂ protons appeared as a doublet at 8.01 and 8.21 ppm, respectively. The H₅-H₈ aromatic protons appeared as a multiplet around 7.40–7.58 ppm. The ¹³C NMR showed the C=O group of methyl ester resonate at 173 ppm, the fullerene (C₆₀) and the Cvz resonate in the region of 157–180 ppm. The sp³ two carbon of C₆₀ appeared at 52.56 and 51.87 ppm, the terminal CH₃ group resonates at 14.27 ppm.

The thermal property of HCvz-C₆₁BM was investigated by TGA and DSC under N₂ atmosphere at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The thermal stability of the acceptors was evaluated at 5% weight loss. The TGA data reveal that the 5% weight loss temperature of HCvz-C₆₁BM was found at 413 °C. The above results indicate that new acceptor is more stable at higher temperature. Glass transition temperature (*T_g*) of HCvz-C₆₁BM observed by DSC, it shows *T_g* at 180 °C. The above TGA and DSC results are strong evidence for newly synthe-

sized acceptor material will not be easily distorted under high temperature during the annealing time. Moreover, after device fabrication durability of the device may be stable.

The photophysical properties of HCvz-C₆₁BM were investigated by UV-Visible absorption spectrophotometer. The UV-Vis spectrum of HCvz-C₆₁BM was measured in CHCl₃ solution (concentration of 10⁻⁵ mol/L) and thin film state and it shows absorption peak at 320 nm and 323 nm, respectively. The absorption band observed a tail shift to longer wavelength region up to 800 nm and it was shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Normalized UV-Visible spectra of PC₆₁BM and HCvz-C₆₁BM in CHCl₃ solution (S) and thin film (F).

The energy level of fullerene derivative was investigated by cyclic voltammetry (CV). The LUMO energy levels of HCvz-C₆₁BM calculated using the equation

LUMO = $-eV (E_{\text{red}}^{\text{onset}} - E_{1/2} \text{ ferrocene} + 4.8)$. Where the $E_{1/2} = 0.35$ V was calculated from the oxidation and reduction potential of ferrocene. The cyclic voltammeter of PC₆₁BM and HCvz-C₆₁BM displays three reversible reduction peaks. LUMO energy levels of PC₆₁BM and HCvz-C₆₁BM were calculated from their first onset reduction potential in CV and we found -0.77 and -0.82 V of onset reduction and their corresponding LUMO values are -3.68 and -3.63 eV, respectively. The synthesized new acceptors possessing slightly higher LUMO value than PC₆₁BM.

The photovoltaic property of HCvz-C₆₁BM was investigated by BHJ-PSC device with different weight ratio of P3HT as donor and HCvz-C₆₁BM as an acceptor. The device structure is ITO/PEDOT/P3HT : HCvz-C₆₁BM/LiF/Al. The weight ratio of P3HT : HCvz-C₆₁BM device was optimized in 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 2 : 1, respectively, among these three conditions the weight ratio of 1 : 2 (P3HT : HCvz-C₆₁BM) active layer device showed best performance such as PCE of 1.74%, Jsc of 6.19 mA/cm², Voc of 0.78 V, FF of 37%. The photovoltaic performances are tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1. Photovoltaic performance of the P3HT and HCvz-C₆₁BM

Device	P3HT : HCvz-C ₆₁ BM (in CHCl ₃)	Jsc (mA/cm ²)	Voc (V)	FF (%)	PCE (%)
1	1 : 1	5.00	0.75	34.90	1.50
2	1 : 2	6.19	0.78	37.58	1.74
3	2 : 1	4.00	0.71	30.40	0.87

Conclusion

We have synthesized carbazole (Cvz) based fullerene acceptor derivative such as HCvz-C₆₁BM. The new acceptor is freely soluble in common chlorinated organic solvents, and it exhibit higher thermal stability and higher LUMO energy level of -3.63 eV. The HCvz-C₆₁BM shows

absorption peak at 320 nm and the absorption band observed a tail shift to longer wavelength region up to 800 nm. The photovoltaic device performance of HCvz-C₆₁BM was achieved PCE of 1.74%, Jsc of 6.19 mA/cm², Voc of 0.78 V, FF of 37%.

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